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The Effect of Bureaucratic and Humanistic Leadership Styles on the Innovative Work Behavior of Employees

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of bureaucratic and humanistic leadership styles on the innovative work behavior of employees. The literature was reviewed to deepen and establish the concept of the study. Descriptive assessment and correlational research design were employed. Data were gathered from the respondents. They were the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag. It was ascertained that the bureaucratic leadership style is high while the humanistic style is moderate. Consequently, this indicates that the bureaucratic style of leadership dominated the humanistic style. A significant correlation was found between leadership styles and innovative work behavior. Hence, the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

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Introduction

Organizational success has been the primary concern that is not always attained through money, but also through the right leadership and management styles that promote positive employee behavior. Leadership is a generic term so one has to define it based on context. Achieving organizational success then is a multidimensional factor of leadership styles and employees' behavior anchored on organizational objectives. Good leadership, a positive environment, and just compensation can motivate employees to perform, and can result in different kinds of behavior such as organizational citizenship behavior (Abun, et al, 2021), entrepreneurial spirit/innovative behavior (Abun, et al. 2021), work engagement (2021) and work performance (Iqbal et al. 2015).

Studies with implausible results were conducted particularly on the effect of different styles of leadership on employees' performance, attitude, and organizational performance have been conducted by many researchers and the results are not conclusive. For example, Fakhri, et al. (2020) studied the effect of transformational and transactional leadership styles on employees' performance and the result showed that transformational leadership is a significant

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predictor of employees' performance. In another instance, Wang's, et al (2019) study showed no correlation between authoritarian leadership and employee performance. On the contrary, the study of Kalu and Okpokwasili (2018) showed otherwise. In terms of organizational change, on one hand, this does not correlate with autocratic leadership (Du, et al. 2019). On the other hand, when transformational, autocratic, and democratic leadership styles were taken together, a positive relationship with organizational performance exists Al Khajeh, 2018). Abun, et al (2021) likewise studied the effect of transformational leadership on the attitude of employees toward the organization; a correlation was found.

Despite skepticism, leadership's vital role is recognized in employees' as well as organizational performance (Amegayibor, 2021, Chua, et al., 2018, Al Khajeh, 2018). However, there have been no studies yet investigating the role of the two leadership styles on employees' innovative behavior.

The researchers are currently connected with educational institutions which are guided by their own rules and that of the government, such as the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) or DepEd (Department of Education) and its own institutional rules. The institution, faculty, and employees cannot do otherwise except follow the given rules, leaving no room for flexibility and autonomy.

The bureaucratic leadership-management style has been criticized to be inhumane but delivers efficiency and productivity. Interestingly, recent scholars have called for the incorporation of human values into business theories, organizations, and management practices (Fu, et. al. 2020, cited from Dierksmeier, 2011; Mackey & Sisodia, 2014). They realized that the mere focus on instrumental values such as profit, wealth, and growth is seriously flawed, ((Mackey and Sisodia, 2014 as cited in Fu, et al. 2020).

On one end, the researcher seriously believes that the institution where he is working is concerned with the process and rules, efficiency, and productivity. The institution in turn, believes that these management practices will lead to growth, quality, and profit. Hence, this premise motivated the researcher to conduct a study on the effect of bureaucratic and humanistic leadership styles on the innovative behavior of employees.

The study is divided into five parts. Primarily, it presents the introduction which explains the background and the objective of the study. Secondly, the literature review is discussed. It examines the existing literature related to the theories of bureaucratic, humanistic leadership styles, and innovative work behavior of employees. The third part is the research methodology which explains the research design of the study, population, locale of the study, gathering procedures, instruments, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth one is the data presentation and analysis where its presentation follows the statement of the problem of the study. The final part covers the discussion of results and discussion, and subsequently presents the conclusion of the study.

Literature Review

The literature review examined the existing discussion on leadership, bureaucratic and humanistic leadership. This provided an in-depth understanding of the topic that strengthened the theories investigated.

Leadership

Authors view leadership from their perspectives. Thus, it is difficult to come up with a single definition, as Winston (2006) explained. Some authors describe leadership from trait characteristics or personal factors such as Stodgill, (1948); Tannenbaum and Schmidt, (1973); CEML, (2002); Harter, (2008). The trait theory of leadership suggests that there are persons who are born with certain characteristics which help them to be good leaders like intelligence, alertness, insight, responsibility, initiative, persistence, self-confidence, and sociability. Other authors describe leadership as behavioral practices. Behavioral theory states that leadership can be learned and developed through education and experience. Under this category, some leaders are oriented toward people and tasks (Lewin et al., 1939; Blake and Mouton, 1964, 1985; Kouzes and Posner, 1995). They are either paying attention to building a good relationship with subordinates and their needs or focusing on tasks that are carried out according to their expectations. However, leaders determine where to focus based on the situation. Applying leadership depends on the context of the

culture of the place. It is along this concept, that Hersey and Blanchard, 1969, 1974; Vroom and Yetton, (1973); Graeff, (1983) claimed that leadership is situational.

There is a need to adopt an integrative definition of leadership that captures the content and the purpose of leadership as described by different authors mentioned earlier. Rost (1991), for example, defined leadership as “an influence relationship among leaders and collaborators who intend significant changes that reflect their mutual purposes”. Kouzes and Posner (1991) also defined leadership as “the art of mobilizing others to want to struggle for shared aspirations”. These two definitions emphasize an ability to influence followers and to achieve organizational goals as shared aspirations or mutual purpose. This concept indicates that leadership exists in social relations. Leaders and followers exist for a common purpose. The ability to influence followers for a common purpose is the concern of leadership.

Influencing followers to achieve organizational objectives may be achieved through different leadership styles such as transactional and transformational (Bass, 1974; Burns, 1978; Price, 2003), and bureaucratic and humanistic leadership styles (Weber, 1966, Fu et al, 2020). The application of these different leadership styles depends on the situation or the type of followers. These leadership styles emphasize two orientations to achieve organizational objectives: task and people. Focusing on tasks and neglecting people will fail, likewise focusing on people and neglecting tasks will also fail. Striking a balance between the two is necessary. These are either transactional and transformational leadership styles or bureaucratic and humanistic leadership styles, this is the focus of the study.

Bureaucratic Leadership

Historically, the term “bureaucracy” was introduced by French philosopher, Vincent de Gourmay, in 1765 (Tierean & Bratucu, 2009). This is taken from the French word “bureaucratie” which is composed of two root words, “bureau” (desk) and “cratie” (a kind of government) (Merriam-Webster, n.d). This word is called red tape since it relies on rules that constrain behavior. The existence of bureaucracy in the government was a call of the time to address the concern of the government because it expanded services during the modern period specifically following the industrial revolution (Tierean & Bratucu, 2009). An unintended consequence of the government’s expansion was corruption and nepotism and to prevent this, it was necessary to introduce bureaucracy to provide checks and balances. The presence of rules and structure in bureaucracy seemed to work well in promoting efficiency and curbing corruption and thus, in its development, bureaucracy is not only applied to the state government but expanded to any organization including the Catholic Church (Abun, et al. 2021).

Based on its historical development, bureaucracy means “a government characterized by specialization of functions, adherence to fixed rules, and a hierarchy of authority” or “a system of administration marked by officialism, red tape, and proliferation” (Merriam-Webster, n.d). The adjective word for bureaucracy is bureaucratic which means having the characteristics of bureaucracy or bureaucrats (Merriam -Webster, n.d). Rockman (n.d) identified five characteristics of bureaucracy and these are jurisdictional competency (specialized functions or defined roles), command and control (there is a hierarchical structure with prescribed functions), continuity (uniform rules and procedures to guide the behavior/standard operating procedures), professionalization of management (requires full-time officials who devote exclusively their time managerial responsibilities) and rules (the lifeblood of bureaucratic organization which requires rules and procedures in the operation).

Oxford Reference (2016) defines a bureaucratic leader as "one who depends on his/her position in a clearly defined hierarchy to influence followers, who adhere to established rules and procedures and who is generally inflexible and suspicious of change". This definition refers to a system of leadership management that relies on established rules, procedures, and a hierarchy of authority to influence followers. A bureaucratic leader has the characteristics of bureaucracy (Huhtala, et al. n.d). The leadership relies on rules to influence followers and followers are expected to follow the rules in carrying out their duties and responsibilities and obey the structure of command. This leadership-management style was introduced by Max Webber (1947) and is considered as the most effective and efficient form of leadership management in an organization. Specifically, all duties and responsibilities are clearly defined and therefore avoid ambiguity (Aydin, 2010). It was considered technically superior to other forms of

management/leadership, though Weber himself and others have criticized it as dehumanizing and making the organization monstrous machines (Weber, 1976, 1978; Clegg, 1990). Weber (1947) identified several characteristics of bureaucracy: a division of labor (specialization), impersonality, the hierarchy of authority (centralization), rules and regulations (formalization), and career orientation. As jobs are too complex, it is necessary to delegate the jobs to several individuals. Hence, positions are created with specific responsibilities as reflected in the organizational chart. All employees perform their duties and responsibilities based on the prescribed descriptions, rules, and procedures given by the organization creating a formal atmosphere (Weber, 1947) of relationships based on structures, functions, and rules (Aron, 1994, Giddens, 1997, cited by Serpa & Ferreira, 2019). Employees are expected to make decisions based on facts, and rules and not on feelings. The line of communication or reporting has to follow the chain of command in which one cannot go immediately to the highest authority without going through proper channels. Therefore, all members have to obey the chain of command of the office. This is another characteristic of the bureaucracy namely the rational definition of office in which duties and responsibilities must be defined (Heckscher & Donnellon, 1994). Consequently, respect is not for the person but for the office. To guide employees' behaviors in carrying out their duties and responsibilities, rules and regulations must be clearly stated (Weber, 1947) and violating these may lead to punishment. Employees must obey the authority and the rules because this is dependent on career advancement. As a result of structures, rules, and regulations, efficiency is established as one important characteristic of bureaucracy. According to Weber (1947), bureaucracy is the structure that maximizes rational decision-making and administrative efficiency.

The role of bureaucratic leadership styles in organizational performance has been studied. The results were varied. Some studies found a negative relationship between bureaucratic leadership style and organizational performance (Al Khajeh, 2018). They do not significantly affect organizational performance (Idrus, et al. 2015) but cause a lower organizational commitment (Idrus, et al., 2015). The study further suggested that it inhibits freedom and consequently hampers innovative behavior (Huhtala, et.al. n.d). Contextually, bureaucratic leadership influences organizational agility and performance in the tax sector (Wijaya, et al. 2021).

Humanistic Leadership

Abun, et al (2021) deplored bureaucratic leadership management because it undermines human relations. Hammel and Zanini (2017) as cited in Abun, et al (2021) disapproved of bureaucratic leadership management based on several counts like *bloating* (creating many layers and managers), *friction* (creating too many processes that delay decision making), *insularity* (too focus on internal problems and neglect to respond to external environment demand), and *disempowerment* (subordinates are not given the power and autonomy to decide on issues they face). Further, Ritzer (2004) criticized it as treating human beings as an impersonal “*iron cage*” or object to be manipulated. There is no autonomy and freedom because it discourages the employees to take a risk. It develops a risk aversion attitude in which the employees are just satisfied with following rules and procedures. They tend to stay on the safe side rather than try new ventures (Ritzer, 2004). Because of those negative effects, many scholars have called for the incorporation of humanistic leadership management into business and management practices (Dierksmeier, 2011; Mackey & Sisodia, 2014).

Humanistic management is not new because it has been existing in theory since it was introduced by Swart (1973), but it was under the shadow of bureaucratic leadership management. The purpose of its integration into leadership-management practice is to solve many negative issues posed by the bureaucratic leadership-management style and develop a new approach to cope with the old problems such as motivation, work satisfaction, morale, and productivity. To understand further the concept of humanistic leadership – management style, one needs to know the meaning of humanism. It is claimed that humanistic leadership is understood alongside humanism.

Originally humanism was a system of education and a mode of inquiry in the 13th and 14th centuries in northern Italy (Grudin, 2020), the origin of studies on humanities. It is connected to western beliefs and philosophies that emphasize the human realm which is also known as renaissance humanism. The effect of such philosophy extends beyond the end of the renaissance era with the proliferation of humanities studies. Corresponding to the historical origin of humanism, Merriam-Webster Dictionary (n.d) defines it as “a devotion to the humanities” or “a devotion to human

welfare”. All modern humanism is referring to modern doctrines like pragmatic humanism, Christian humanism, and secular humanism. The 20th-century humanism doctrine like that of Ferdinand C. Scott Schiller (pragmatic humanist), and Jacques Maritain (Christian humanist), are all showing anthropocentric emphasis (Grudin, 2020). Correspondingly, Cambridge Dictionary defines humanism as “a system of thought and reasoning based on human values and interests.”

Cambridge dictionary defines “humanistic” as “treating people with respect and making certain they are safe, happy, healthy.”. When a humanistic word is combined with leadership, then we have humanistic leadership which offers similar ideas. Fu, et al (2020) defined humanistic leadership as one that offers humanistic care, treats people as holistic human beings, pursues their human development, and takes care of the interest of the common good. According to Fu, et al. (2020), different cultures have different definitions of humanistic leadership, however, they all emphasize human beings and their need to be the center of attention. Aktouf and Holford (2009) expand and put a concrete perspective of what humanistic leadership means. For them, humanistic leadership means allowing the human person to self-determine how they carry out the work that can give meaning to them. Related to this concept, Fritz and Sörgel (2017) reasoned that the top-down approach of management is inadequate for humanistic leadership because it should not impose the purpose of work extrinsically or externally. Leaders should not impose what the employees want, but allow them to have the freedom to achieve goals. This is emphasized by Mele (2016) as he asserted that leadership moves away from the boss and the power is given to the employees. It fosters a good relationship and dialogue between the leader and the follower. Fritz and Sörgel (2017) added that leaders must show concern for individual needs and personal growth of the individual. Congruently, Peus and Frey (2009) identified several characteristics of humanistic leadership which are: first, *autonomy* in which employees are allowed to find meaning and mission at work. The second is *transparency*. It allows members to know what is going on in their company and this can be done through transparency by sharing information and open communication. The third is *participation*. It allows the employees or subordinates to participate in discussion and decision-making and even in the formulation of vision, mission, and goals. Fourth is *justice*. It allows justice to rule the workplace. Fifth is *constructive feedback*. Both leaders, and followers are open to receiving feedback for the improvement of work. Lastly, the humanistic leader should *serve as a role model* as Hayat and Suliman (2013) underscored that leaders need to express and practice integrity. A leader inspires follower so live moral values in the workplace.

Studies on the effect of humanistic leadership on organizational performance can be considered few because this is a new area of research. In terms of its effect on organizational performance, Daley (1986) found that humanistic leadership-management practice moderately affects organizational success. Concerning other aspects of the organization, Hu, et al (2018) studied the relationship between humanistic leadership-management and corporate social responsibility and the study found that managerial humanistic attention positively affects corporate social responsibility. A similar finding was also presented in the study of Abun, et al (2021) that humanistic leadership styles affect the organizational citizenship behavior of employees. In a similar vein, Wang, et al (2021) studied the effect of leaders' pro-social orientation on organizational affective commitment and organizational citizenship behavior and the study found that leaders' pro-social behavior which leaders are paying attention to the needs of employees has significantly affected the affective commitment and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) This is also confirmed by the study of Vui-Yee (2016) whereby organizations that practice humanistic responsibility have a significant impact on employee commitment. In the context of educational institutions, Effendi et. al (2019) conducted a study concerning the effect of a humanistic approach to the principal's leadership on the strengthening of character education. The study found that a humanistic approach to the principal's leadership significantly affects the optimization of character education in schools.

Innovative Work Behavior: Psychological and Organizational Factors

To understand the concept of innovative behavior, one needs to understand the word or the concept of innovation within the organization. Porter (1990) identified three cornerstones for global competitiveness namely innovation, continuous improvement, and change. Porter's view indicates that innovation is not a simple issue in the organization,

but it is something to reckon with. Therefore, one needs to understand what innovation entails. Merriam-Webster defines innovation as "a new idea, method, or device" or "the introduction of something new". "It refers to something new or a change made to an existing product, idea, or field". Thus, this definition gives the idea that innovation is not the same as an invention which refers to something new that previously has not been in existence (Merriam-Webster, n.d). Similarly, Cambridge Dictionary (n.d) defines innovation as "the development of new products, designs or ideas". While Collins Dictionary defines it as "a new thing or new method of doing things". So, based on these definitions and in the context of the current investigation, this paper defines innovation as "finding a new way of doing things". This definition provides an idea that one is not required to always follow the existing practice of doing things, this is termed as innovative behavior.

Yuan and Marquardt (2021) defined this as "the introduction and application of new ideas, products, processes, and procedures to a person's work role, work unit, or organization". Yuan Marquardt asserted that innovative work behavior does not only refer to individual work behavior, but also organizational behavior. Merdan (2022) defines innovative behavior as "the behavior that contributes to the individual and the organization's self-development and easy adaptation to the rapid change". This definition suggests that rapid changes in the external environment required response for rapid adaptation within the organization which requires innovative behavior. Martínez-Alonso, et al (2020) likewise, defined it as the "intentional introduction of a person into the application of new ideas, products, processes, and procedures at the workplace or in the firm". The external environment is constantly changing which requires adjustment, and adaptation to the products, services, processes, and procedures. Maintaining old ways of doing things will not bring the organization to par with the dynamic external environment. Those definitions that were identified indicate that innovative work behavior is focused on the generation, introduction, or application of ideas, processes, procedures, and new products (Stan, et al., 2014).

Analyzing innovative behavior is a complex one because personal and organizational aspects come into play. Purc and Lagun (2019) investigated in their study that personal values affect the innovative behavior of workers. This is also confirmed by the study of Li and Zheng (2014) that one factor that influences innovative behavior is psychological capital. In terms of psychological capital, Siregar, et al. (2019) identified competence, self-efficacy, motivation, and organizational commitment as factors that influence innovative work behavior. Yuan and Woodman (2010) stated that these psychological capitals are shaped by contextual and individual differences including organizational support for innovation, supervisor relationship quality, job requirement for innovativeness, employee reputation as innovative, and individual dissatisfaction. These are the reasons why Popa, et al (2010) asserted that the innovation process is complex and multidimensional since it involves many factors. It is not just relied on institutional resources but also depends on the motivation and organizational climate that encourages innovative ideas. The study of Riaz, et. al (2018) confirmed the relationship between organizational factors and innovative behavior as they found that organizational support for innovation is correlated to the innovative work behavior of employees. Thus, based on these findings, it is very clear that innovative behavior is a consequence of psychological, individual, and organizational factors (Sameer & Ohly, 2017, Voo, et. al, 2019), as indicated by the study of Scott and Bruce (1994) that leadership, individual factors, and the perception of climate for innovations affect the innovative behavior. Related to individual factors, the study by Hewko (2022) found that individual factors are significantly more predictive of employees' innovative work behavior than organizational factors. This finding may not be conclusive because the previous one was found otherwise. The study by Chatchawan, et al. (2017) found that organizational climate, learning orientation, organizational support, and transformational leadership affect the innovative work behavior of the employees.

Studies have shown that innovative work behavior contributes to the organization's competitiveness and performance. For example, Aitbar, et al (2016) studied the impact of innovative work behavior on the organization's competitiveness and found that it influences the competitive position of the organization. The same is true with the performance. Susilo and Susilo (2019) conducted a study on the effect of innovative work behavior on work performance and the study found that it is a strong predictor of organizational performance.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Abun, et al (2021), Fritz, S. & Sörgel, P. (2017) and Australian Government Innovative Work Environment Scale (2022).

Figure 1: The conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between the independent variables namely bureaucratic leadership and humanistic leadership and innovative work behavior.

Statement of the Problems

The study examined the effect of bureaucratic and humanistic leadership styles on innovative work behavior. It specifically answered the following questions:

1. What is the bureaucratic leadership style of the administrators of the institution?
2. What is the humanistic leadership style of the administrators of the institution?
3. What is the innovative work behavior of the employees/faculty of the institution?
4. Is there a relationship between leadership styles and the innovative work behavior of the employees?

Assumption

The study assumed that leadership styles affect the innovative work behavior of employees and they can be measured.

Hypothesis

Organizational climate and leadership have been considered significant predictors of innovative work behavior of employees (Scott and Bruce (1994). The current study also argues that leadership style affects the innovative work behavior of employees.

Scope and delimitation of the Study

The study covered the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag in Ilocos Norte and delimits its investigation into the leadership styles particularly bureaucratic and humanistic leadership styles and their effect on the innovative behavior of employees.

Research Methodology

The research followed a specific method of investigation. Wilkinson, (2000), and Leedy, (1974) opined that research methodology is an established process for conducting the inquiry. It applies certain methods to determine, select, and analyze the data related to the concerned topic, The study applied certain methods of investigation such as research design, data gathering instruments method, the population of the study, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and the statistical treatment of data.

Research Design of the Study

The research design of the study is the descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design. Ariola (2006) explained that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. In short, it answers the questions what, when, how, and where (McCombes, 2020).

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag. This college is in Laoag City, the capital of Ilocos Norte.

Population

The respondents of the study were the employees of the college. Since the number of employees was limited, the total enumeration sampling.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adopted validated questionnaires by the Australian Government (2022) on innovative work behavior and Abun, et.al (2021) and Fritz, and Sörgel, (2017) on leadership styles (Bureaucratic and Humanistic).

Data Gathering Procedures

To preserve the integrity of scientific research, the data were gathered after the approval of the president of the college. The researcher sent a letter to the president and after the letter was approved, the questionnaires were distributed, collected, and submitted by the researcher's representative.

Ethical Procedures

The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the content of the paper which neither violated ethical standards nor caused harm to human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The weighted mean determined the level of leadership style, and innovative work behavior of employees and Pearson r measured the correlation between leadership styles and innovative work behavior. The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly Agree/ Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree / High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat Agree/ Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly Disagree/Very Low</i>

Data Presentation and Analysis

This part presents the data that was gathered through research questionnaires which were analyzed. The presentation of data is in the table and then the analysis is below the table. The structure of the presentation follows the statement of the problem.

Problem 1: What is the bureaucratic leadership style of the administrators of the institution?

Table 1. Bureaucratic Leadership Style of the Administrators of the Institution

INDICATORS	Mean	DI
1. Employees are required to follow specific rules formulated by the authority/institution.	4.31	SA
2. Leaders follow the rule of the book to keep the team in the right direction.	4.19	A
3. The leaders tend to prefer rigid rules and regulations to flexibility.	4.14	A
4. All employees must follow the established rules and procedures.	4.25	SA
5. There is little action taken until a supervisor or a higher-up approves a decision.	4.07	A
6. Even small matters have to be referred to someone higher up for the final answer.	4.08	A

7. In general, a person who wants to make his/her own decisions would be quickly discouraged	4.02	A
8. Employees are working under the close monitoring of their supervisor.	4.13	A
9. One cannot do his/her job in his/her way but he/she has to follow the rules and procedures.	4.14	A
10. Communications, decisions, and proceedings are put in writing for future reference.	4.16	A
11. Employees are afraid of violating the rules because it means punishment.	4.08	A
Composite Mean	4.14	A

Source: Abun, et al., (2021), and Fritz, and Sörgel, (2017)

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *strongly agree/ Very High*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree / High*
- 2.61-3.40 *somewhat agree/ Moderate*
- 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
- 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low*

The bureaucratic leadership style of the respondents gained a composite mean of 4.14 which is interpreted as "agree or high". Taking it singly, most of the items that measure bureaucratic leadership style are evaluated within the same mean range level such as preferring rigid rules and regulations (4.14), following the rule of the book (4.19), no action is done without the approval of higher-ups (4.07), working under close monitoring (4.13), strictly following rules and procedures (4.14). The administrators were evaluated very highly along with "requiring employees to follow specific rules formulated by the authority or institution". This result indicates that the institution are bureaucratic. On one hand, bureaucratic leadership has been praised and on the other hand, is blamed. Reynolds (2018) pointed out that one of the good characteristics of bureaucratic management (among five others) is efficiency in which one accomplishes an objective with little time and effort by following the rules and procedures, the objectives can be achieved. On the other hand, Hammel and Zanini (2017) criticized bureaucratic management as a form of disempowerment because it does not empower the employees to make decisions and to do things in their way. Earlier, Ritzer (2004) criticized bureaucratic management as treating men as an impersonal "iron cage" of rule-based, rational control. In other words, managers treat their employees as machines.

Problem 2: What is the humanistic leadership style of the administrators of the institution?

Table 2. Humanistic Leadership Style of the Administrators of the Institution

INDICATORS	Mean	DI
1. The employees are enabled to decide what concerns them.	3.34	SWA
2. Budget decisions are moved toward employees.	3.19	SWA
3. The leader takes a supporting role instead of a directive one.	3.26	SWA
4. Leader supports the strengths of employees by Shaping and designing the work environment.	3.32	SWA
5. The leader takes the role of an advisor, not a decision-maker.	3.28	SWA
6. The leader does not control budgets and bills but promotes self-responsibility.	3.29	SWA
7. If employees do not feel well in a system the leader would initiate a change toward a system that is better for the employee.	3.31	SWA
8. The leader attempts to give employees the subjects for which they are passionate.	3.29	SWA
9. Leader aims at offering employees a working environment with creative leeway.	3.25	SWA
10. Leader emphasizes the importance of appreciation and respect.	3.35	SWA
11. The leader acts as a role model in promoting appreciation.	3.34	SWA
12. Leader respects and appreciates the individual needs wants, wishes, and situations.	3.34	SWA
13. The leader agrees that it is essential to foster individual involvement.	3.37	SWA
14. The leader acts authentically and ethically.	3.37	SWA
15. The leader wants to foster individual passions.	3.34	SWA
16. Employees follow self-set goals and are not motivated by the promise of promotion.	3.35	SWA
17. Leaders protect employees from overwork and demand regeneration time.	3.32	SWA

18. Employees can be themselves and feel secure as they are accepted as they are.	3.37	SWA
19. The communal spirit is actively fostered by leaders.	3.39	SWA
20. Employees perceive that human flourishing is more important than economic growth.	3.35	SWA
Composite Mean	3.32	SWA

Source: Abun, et al., (2021) and Fritz, and Sörgel, (2017)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly Agree/ Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree / High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat Agree/ Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly Disagree/Very Low</i>

The humanistic leadership style of the respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.32 which is interpreted as "somewhat agree or moderate". This result indicates that the administrators of the institution practice humanistic leadership style to a moderate extent. Taking the items singly, it shows that all items under the humanistic leadership style are evaluated within the same level of the mean range which is all interpreted as "somewhat agree or moderate". It indicates that administrators practice a humanistic leadership style only to a moderate level in the area of enabling employees to decide what concerns them, promoting self-responsibility, creating an environment for creativity, emphasizing the importance of appreciation and respect, accepting employees as they are, promoting individual development, protecting employees from overwork, allowing employees to set their own work goals, fostering communal spirit, acting as a role model for employees, allowing the employees to direct their work, appreciating individual needs, wishes and situations, and fostering individual passions. These humanistic elements are summarized by Mele (2006) into seven elements: wholeness, comprehensive knowledge, human dignity, development, common good, transcendence, and stewardship-sustainability.

Problem3: What is the innovative work behavior of the employees/faculty of the institution?

Table 3. Innovative Work Behaviour of the Employees/Faculty of the Institution

INDICATORS	Mean	DI
1. Demonstrate positive reception of ideas from others and provide constructive ideas or advice.	3.46	A
2. Established and maintain relationships based on mutual respect and trust.	3.48	A
3. Participate in collaborative work arrangements to foster innovation.	3.44	A
4. Acknowledge suggestions, improvements, and innovations from a colleague.	3.41	A
5. Encourage the innovative practice of others.	3.38	SWA
6. Facilitate and participate in collaborative work arrangements to foster innovation.	3.38	SWA
7. Take the courage to introduce new ideas to change the existing/old practice.	3.45	A
8. Take the initiative to gain new knowledge and skills related to the current job.	3.45	A
9. Proactively share relevant information, knowledge, and skills with colleagues.	3.43	A
10. Take a considered risk to perform the job in a different way to achieve the objective.	3.42	A
11. Find appropriate ways of celebrating and promoting innovation with colleagues.	3.46	A
Composite Mean	3.43	A

Source: Australian Government (2022)

The data reveals the innovative work behavior of employees obtained a composite mean of 3.43 which is interpreted as "agree or high". This result suggests that employees are innovative to a high degree in terms of welcoming ideas from others and providing constructive ideas or advice, maintaining relationships based on mutual respect and trust, participating in collaborative work arrangements to foster innovation, acknowledging suggestions, improvements and innovations from a colleague, encouraging the innovative practice of others, facilitating and participating in collaborative work arrangements to foster innovation, taking the courage to introduce new ideas to change the existing/old practice, taking the initiative to gain new knowledge and skills related to the current job, sharing relevant

information, knowledge, and skills with colleagues, taking a considered risk to perform the job in a different way to achieve the objective, and finding appropriate ways of celebrating and promoting innovation with colleagues. These behaviors must be promoted through empowering leadership (Rao - Jada, et al., 2019) and innovative leadership (Torres, et al., 2017) and by enhancing the determinants of innovative work behavior of employees, individual work performance and organizational performance can be achieved (Hussain, et al, 2022).

Problem 4: Is there a relationship between leadership styles and the innovative work behavior of the employees?

Table 4. Relationship Between Leadership Styles and the Innovative Work Behavior of the Employees

		Bureaucratic Leadership Style	Humanistic Leadership Style	Innovative Work Behaviour
Bureaucratic Leadership Style	Pearson Correlation	1	-.196*	-.312**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.010	.000
	N	170	170	170
Humanistic Leadership Style	Pearson Correlation	-.196*	1	.814**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010		.000
	N	170	170	170
Innovative Work Behavior	Pearson Correlation	-.312**	.814**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	170	170	170

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on the Pearson r correlation analysis, it shows that there is a significant correlation at 0.01 level (2-tailed) between bureaucratic, humanistic leadership styles and innovative work behavior of employees. This result suggests that both, bureaucratic, and humanistic leadership style affects the innovative work behavior of employees. Improvement along with leadership styles can significantly affect the innovative work behavior of employees.

Results and Discussion

The study ascertained the effect of bureaucratic and humanistic leadership styles on the innovative work behavior of employees and based on the Pearson r correlation analysis, there is a significant correlation between both leadership styles and the employees' innovative work behavior. This finding indicates that practicing bureaucratic and humanistic leadership styles affect the innovative work behavior of employees. Though the study of Alheet, et al. (2020) found a negative correlation between transactional leadership style (bureaucratic leadership style) and innovative work behavior of employees, contextually, Divine Word College of Laoag's practice of bureaucratic leadership style is significantly correlated to innovative work behavior. This result indicates that context can make a difference in the result of certain leadership practices. Divine Word College of Laoag reflects that the more bureaucratic the administrators are, the more innovative the employees become. The conflicting finding from another study can be explained by the context or the organizational culture differences because these often play a mediating role in the formation of behavior (Khan, et al., 2020). In other words, other organizational cultures facilitate the bureaucratic leadership style to produce innovative work behavior. Thus, the effect of bureaucratic leadership styles may not necessarily result in negative innovative work behavior. This may also depend on other cultural factors of the organization, organizational climate, or other existing conditions (Scott and Bruce, 1994, Janssen et al., 2004). The result of certain leadership practices depends on the context such as organizational culture and climate (Jin, et al., 2022). Therefore, it is important to study the effect of organizational culture and climate on innovative work behavior.

In terms of the effect of humanistic leadership styles on innovative work behavior, the study also suggests that

humanistic leadership practice affects innovative work behavior. This indicates that the more humanistic the administrators are, the more innovative the employees become. This result corresponds to another on the effect of ethical leadership on innovative work behavior (Iqbal, et al., 2020). Treating employees as individual persons with dignity motivate employees to be innovative. It further explains that management or leadership is both rational and humane activity (Waddock, 2016). It just means that practicing pure bureaucratic leadership may not promote innovative work behavior without a humane approach to management or leadership. As Waddock (2016) added that humanizing the system and integrating ethics in leadership is important for administrators to deliver and promote innovative work behavior.

Conclusion

The study aimed to determine the effect of bureaucratic and humanistic leadership styles on the innovative work behavior of employees. The bureaucratic leadership style of the administrators is considered high, while the humanistic leadership is moderate and lower than the bureaucratic leadership style. It just concludes that the dominant leadership style of administrators is bureaucratically followed by a humanistic style. It was further found that the innovative work behavior of employees was also high. Despite the bureaucratic style, the employees are still practicing innovative work behavior.

The Pearson r correlation result shows that there is a significant correlation between bureaucratic and humanistic styles and the innovative work behavior of the employees. It concludes that both leadership styles affect the innovative work behavior of employees. It suggests that the more bureaucratic and humanistic the administrators are, the more innovative the employees become. It is recommended then that the administrators need to enhance their bureaucratic and humanistic leadership styles. It is noteworthy that leadership and management accompanied by rational and humane approaches, achieve organizational success.

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